

Three sources introduced *Pomacea* spp. in the Philippines:

P. canaliculata via Taiwan from Argentina to Lemery, Batangas, Luzon, 1982.

P. gigas from Florida (USA) to Makati, Metro Manila, 1983.

Pomacea snails directly from Argentina to Asturias, Cebu, in 1984. An African snail, *Pila*

leopardivillensis d'Orbigny, was also introduced from Taiwan. *P. cuprina* (Reeve) is also found in the Philippines. □

Soil and Crop Management

Puddling methods for lowland rice

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We studied the effect of puddling methods on lowland rice (Paiyur 1 variety) during Jun-Sep kharif and Oct-Jan (winter) seasons 1982-83. Puddling twice with an iron plow followed by one puddling with a helical blade puddler produced the highest grain yield and net income (see table). □

Effect of puddling method on grain yield and return. Tamil Nadu, India.

Puddling method	Grain yield (t/ha)		Cost of cultivation (\$/ha)		Net income (\$/ha)	
	Kharif	Winter	Kharif	Winter	Kharif	Winter
Puddling 3 times with iron plow (conventional)	6.0	4.7	353	339	625	424
Puddling twice with iron plow and once with helical blade puddler	6.4	5.0	337	323	701	492
Puddling twice with country plow and once with helical blade puddler	5.4	4.2	321	329	562	354
Puddling once with iron plow and twice with helical blade puddler	5.7	4.4	327	313	604	401
CD (0.05)	0.6	0.4				

Effect of spacing and seedlings per hill

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We studied the effect of spacing and seedlings per hill in the 1985 dry season. Short-duration rice variety ADT36 was transplanted at 60 d after seeding.

The experiment used 3 spacings (12.5 × 10.0 cm with 80 hills/m², 15.0 × 10.0 cm with 66 hills/m², and 20.0 × 10.0 cm with 50 hills/m² and 2, 4, 6, and 8 seedlings per hill in a randomized block design. NPK at 75-17-31 kg/ha were applied. N was split: 50% as basal, 25% 15 d after transplanting (DT), and 25% 30 DT.

The primary tillers produced panicles, within 21 DT, but these panicles shattered before harvest.

In spite of reduced tillers/hill, panicle weight, and number of filled spikelets/panicle, 12.5- × 10.0-cm spacing produced significantly higher

Effect of spacing and seedlings/hill on yield parameters of short-duration rice. ^a Tamil Nadu, India, 1985 dry season.

Treatment	Tillers/hill	Tillers/m ²	Panicle weight (g)	Spikelets/panicle	Grain yield (t/ha)
<i>Spacing</i>					
12.5 × 10.0 cm	6.6 b	528 a	1.41 a	46 b	4.0 a
15.0 × 10.0 cm	7.0 a	425 b	1.44 a	51 ab	3.6 b
20.0 × 10.0 cm	7.3 a	371 c	1.48 a	53 a	3.3 c
<i>Seedlings/hill</i>					
2	7.4 a	466 a	1.81 a	62 a	4.8 a
4	6.9 ab	442 b	1.38 b	50 b	3.6 b
6	6.7 ab	422 c	1.35 b	47 b	3.1 c
8	6.6 b	416 c	1.21 c	41 c	2.9 c

^a In a column within each group, means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level.

grain yield, mainly because of higher numbers of tillers/unit area (see table).

Increasing the number of

seedlings/hill had an adverse effect. All yield parameters were reduced with more than 2 seedlings/hill. □

Performance of rice varieties on floating rafts

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Rice cultivation on floating rafts, a technique developed at the College of Agriculture, is suitable for flooded areas (see figure). The system saves the labor and electricity needed to drain an area for a single dry season rice crop. Rice